

MODELING HYPERVELOCITY-IMPACT RESPONSE OF CFRP-AI/HC LAMINATE

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ABSTRACT

Advanced composite materials have been increasingly employed in aerospace structures in the last decades due to their low weight and high stiffness. CFRP/Al-HC (carbon-fibre-reinforced plastic face-sheets/aluminium honeycomb-core) sandwich panels typically find their application in satellite structures. In the absence of proper shielding, these structures can be often exposed to impacts by space debris. Thus, a deeper understanding of mechanical response of composites to such impacts is vital to design structures with improved resistance.

This paper is focussed on development of a finite-element (FE) model of hyper-velocity impact behaviour (with velocities up to 1 km/s) of a CFRP-Al/HC sandwich panel. Numerical simulations were carried out using general-purpose FE software Abaqus/ Explicit. A user-defined material model (VUMAT) was developed to study failure of CFRP face sheets using combined Hashin and Puck criteria, while damage of Al/HC was analysed with the Johnson–Cook damage model. A hydrodynamic response was captured employing a Mie-Grüneisen equation of state, and a smooth-particle-hydrodynamics technique was used selectively in the region of impact to model dynamic spallation. A process of interply delamination was modelled with cohesive-zone elements. Numerical results obtained with the developed FE model were compared with experimental data; a reasonable correlation was shown and they provided a useful insight into impact-induced damage of the laminate. Fibre failure was the major damage mode for the cases when penetration was observed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials such as CFRP/Al-HC (carbon-fibre-reinforced plastic face sheets/aluminium honeycomb core) sandwich panels typically find their application in satellite structures due to their excellent mechanical properties such as high specific strength, stiffness and ability to provide tailored properties. In the absence of proper shielding, these structures can be often exposed to impacts by space debris. Many satellites already employ honeycomb sandwich panels with CFRP face-sheets covered by multi-layer thermal insulation as external walls [1]. Furthermore, FRPs are often used in the construction of spacecraft components such as antenna struts, low-distortion frames and lightweight robotic arms [2-5].

Still, many concerns remain about the possibility of employing polymer-matrix composites as the primary satellite structure for long-duration missions because of severe environmental conditions in space. One of the major problems is related to the vulnerability to impact damage from meteoroids and man-made space debris that populate the near-Earth orbital environment. Such particles travel at speeds of several km/s, thus presenting a serious hazard for existing satellites. Previous research found that damage due to high-velocity impacts (HVIs) on composite materials consists of an impact crater,

surface peeling of outer laminae on both the front and rear sides of the plate and significant internal delamination around the impact point that can lead to severe degradation of material's mechanical strength. Moreover, if a hypervelocity particle has enough energy to fully perforate the impacted plate, a debris cloud emerging from the rear face of the target can significantly damage adjacent structures and internal components of the spacecraft.

This study focuses on the development of a finite-element (FE) model to simulate HVI behaviour (with velocities up to 1 km/s) of a CFRP-Al/HC sandwich panel using general-purpose FE software Abaqus/Explicit [6]. A user-defined material model (VUMAT) developed to study damage of CFRP face sheets employing combined Hashin and Puck criteria was used, while interply damage was modelled by means of cohesive-zone elements. A hydrodynamic response of Al-HC was captured using a Mie-Grüneisen equation of state, and its damage was modelled using a Johnson-Cook dynamic failure model. The developed FE model was validated with experimental data from Wicklein *et al.* [7] and showed a reasonable correlation between experimental and numerical damage patterns.

2 FINITE-ELEMENT MODEL

A quarter of the full geometry of the sandwich plate was modelled owing to its symmetry about relevant planes; this resulted in significantly reduced computational efforts. A steel projectile of 3 mm diameter was impacted on the sandwich structure with an impact velocity ranging from 700 m/s to 1 km/s. The general contact algorithm in ABAQUS/explicit [6] was used to simulate contact conditions between the projectile and the composite face-sheets and Al/HC as well as between the layers of CFRP laminate by defining appropriate contact-pair properties. The setup of the developed FE model is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Setup of FE model

An elastic response of CFRP laminate was accounted for; it is discussed in Section 2.1. An element-deletion approach was used to model a material-erosion process based on initiation and evolution of damage in the meshed elements. Criteria for damage initiation and evolution are

discussed in Section 2.2.

2.1 Response of UD composite laminate

An elastic stress-strain relationship for a unidirectional (UD) composite ply was introduced assuming an orthotropic damaged elasticity response. Its constitutive behaviour before damage is expressed using a generalised Hooke's law in the tensorial form:

$$\{\sigma\} = C \{\varepsilon\} . \quad (1)$$

The effect of strain-rate on elastic moduli and strength was defined in order to accurately account for a high-strain-rate response of the laminated composite material. It should be noted that for carbon/epoxy-like systems, where carbon fibres are brittle and show no strain-rate dependence, the strain-hardening at higher loading rates is entirely due to the epoxy matrix; while in glass/epoxy-like systems both glass fibres and the epoxy matrix may contribute towards this.

The strain-rate effects in the elastic and shear moduli are defined by the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} E(\dot{\varepsilon}) &= E(\dot{\varepsilon}_0) \left[m_e \log \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon}}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0} \right) + 1 \right] \\ G(\dot{\gamma}) &= G(\dot{\gamma}_0) \left[m_s \log \left(\frac{\dot{\gamma}}{\dot{\gamma}_0} \right) + 1 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $E(\dot{\varepsilon})$ and $G(\dot{\gamma})$ are elastic and shear moduli for a given strain rate, $E(\dot{\varepsilon}_0)$ and $G(\dot{\gamma}_0)$ are elastic and shear moduli at the reference strain rates $\dot{\varepsilon}_0$ and $\dot{\gamma}_0$, respectively, in three directions and three planes of a 3D co-ordinate system. m_e and m_s are the material parameters obtained by fitting a curve to the experimentally obtained data. The effects of strain rate on ply strength are discussed in the following sections, where initiation of different damage modes is considered.

2.1.1 Damage initiation

Modelling of composites and their damage at a laminate level typically requires input of several parameters, including homogenised ply properties, interply strength and information about the laminate lay-up. Here, a layer-by-layer modelling strategy was adopted to capture failure in each ply. This offers several advantages. First, full 3D stress states can be analysed. Typically, FE models of composite deformation involve the use of 2D shell elements to simulate composite plies, which do not allow accurate representation of stress distributions through the composite thickness. Secondly, intraply and interply damage can be introduced discretely along with phenomenological models that account for complex interaction between them.

Here, a material model offering a combination of Hashin's [7] and Puck's [8] failure criteria was used to implement the advantages of both. The Hashin's criteria were employed to estimate damage in carbon fibres while damage in epoxy matrix was modelled using the Puck's criteria. The empirical forms of these criteria are discussed below.

(A) Fibre damage

- in tension

Here, tensile failure of fibres is defined as a function of tensile strength of laminae along the fibre direction as well as shear strength in transverse directions (in and out of plane). The empirical relation is expressed in the following form:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_{1t}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}} \right)^2 \geq 1, \quad d_{ft} = 1 ; \quad (3)$$

where X_{1r} is the tensile strength of a composite in the fibre direction, while S_{12} and S_{13} are its shear strengths in 1-2 and 1-3 planes, respectively. d_{ft} is a scalar damage variable indicating fibre damage in tension such that $0 \leq d_{ft} \leq 1$, with 0 representing absence of damage, while 1 indicating a fully-damaged state; this nomenclature applies to all the damage modes discussed below. Here, X_{1r} is assumed equal to its quasi-static magnitude since fibres show negligible strain-rate dependence (or none) at high loading rates.

- in compression

Longitudinal compressive failure of composites is driven by shear mechanisms in an intricate way. A first crack might be started by shear fracture of fibres followed by rotation and in-plane shearing of the matrix at a crack tip, which, in turn, promotes kink-band development.

The empirical relation for this damage mode is expressed in the following form:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{K(\dot{\epsilon})X_{1c}^{qs}} \right) + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{K(\dot{\gamma})S_{12}^{qs}} \right) + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{K(\dot{\gamma})S_{13}^{qs}} \right) \geq 1, \quad d_{fc} = 1; \quad (4)$$

the scaling parameter K is defined as:

$$K = \frac{S_{12}^{dyn}(\dot{\gamma}_{12})}{S_{12}^{qs}} = \frac{S_{23}^{dyn}(\dot{\gamma}_{13})}{S_{13}^{qs}}. \quad (5)$$

Here, $S_{12}^{dyn}(\dot{\gamma}_{12})$ and $S_{23}^{dyn}(\dot{\gamma}_{13})$ are in-plane and out-of-plane shear strengths of a ply under dynamic loading conditions at a given strain rate, and S_{12}^{qs} and S_{23}^{qs} are its shear strengths under quasi-static loading conditions.

(B) Matrix damage

Phenomenological matrix-failure criteria for 3D quasi-static failure analysis of UD composites were previously formulated by Puck and Schürmann [8]. These criteria forms a basis of the approach presented here. The applicability of the tensile and compressive failure criteria for quasi-static loading conditions originally proposed was extended to a model material's response under dynamic loading conditions.

The polymer matrix material in a CFRP composite demonstrates strain-rate-sensitivity at high strain rates ($\sim 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), which are typical for high-velocity impact events. This effect becomes significant, particularly in transverse directions, where the polymer matrix is a primary load-bearing constituent. An approach, similar to that employed in modelling compressive failure of fibres was adopted here to account for strain-rate sensitivity. The following criteria were proposed to model failure in the matrix material in compression and tension:

$$\left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{K(\dot{\epsilon})X_{2t}^{qs}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{K(\dot{\gamma})S_{12}^{qs}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{K(\dot{\gamma})S_{23}^{qs}} \right)^2 \right] + \sigma_{22} \left(\frac{1}{K(\dot{\epsilon})X_{2t}^{qs}} + \frac{1}{K(\dot{\epsilon})X_{2c}^{qs}} \right) = 1 \quad (6)$$

$\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33} > 0, dm_t = 1$ (matrix tensile failure)

$\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33} < 0, dm_c = 1$ (matrix compressive failure)

2.1.2 Damage evolution

To alleviate mesh dependency during strain softening in simulations, a characteristic length L_c of a finite element was introduced into the formulation so that the constitutive law was expressed as a stress-displacement relation as shown in Fig. 2.

A positive slope of the stress-displacement curve prior to damage initiation corresponds to a linear-elastic material behaviour; while the negative slope after damage initiation is achieved by evolution of

damage parameter d as follows:

$$d_i = \frac{\delta_{eq}^{f_i} (\delta_{eq} - \delta_{eq}^0)}{\delta_{eq} (\delta_{eq}^{f_i} - \delta_{eq}^0)} \quad (7)$$

Figure 2: Concept of equivalent stress vs. equivalent displacement in evolution of damage variable

Thus, strain is expressed in terms of the deformation of the meshed element (δ) and its characteristic length (L_c) such that $\delta_{eq}^{0 < \delta < f} = L_c \cdot \varepsilon$ (for a typical hexahedral mesh, L_c represents the shortest distance between diagonally opposite nodes of a smallest element). Here, δ_{eq}^0 is the equivalent displacement at the damage initiation, and δ_{eq}^f is the equivalent displacement, at which the material is completely damaged. $i = f_i, f_c, m_i$ and m_c correspond to damage variables associated with failure modes of fibre and matrix materials in tension and compression, respectively. The equivalent displacement at failure was expressed as:

$$\delta_{eq}^f = \frac{2G_f}{\sigma_{eq}^0} \quad (8)$$

Here, G_f is the fracture energy. The elastic and strength properties for CFRP composite laminates were adopted from [7] and [11]. The mechanical and shock-related properties for the Al-HC core were obtained from the manufacturer's catalogue, and the Abaqus technical brief [10], respectively, owing to identical material systems. These are listed in Table 1.

<i>For Mie-Grüneisen EOS model</i>		<i>For Johnson-Cook plasticity and failure model</i>			
Reference density [kg/m ³]	2700	A [MPa]	324.1	C	0.002
Grüneisen coefficient	1.97	B [MPa]	113.8	$\dot{\varepsilon}_0$ (1/s)	1
Wave speed [m/s]	5240	n	0.42		
Parameter s	1.40	θ_{melt} [K]	925		
Reference temperature [K]	293.2	$\theta_{transition}$ [K]	293.2		
Specific heat [J/kg K]	885	m	1.34		

Table 1. Material properties for Al 6061-T6 core

2.1.3 Element deletion

An element-deletion approach [11] used to remove failed elements from the mesh was based on the magnitude of damage variables, $d_i = f_i, f_c, m_i, m_c$ as calculated using Eq. (7) applied to discrete damage modes in the composite laminate. An element was removed when the magnitude of any of the damage variables associated with the fibre failure reached d_{\max} ($= 1$) at an integration point of the element. When this condition was satisfied, the element was removed from the mesh, and it offered no subsequent resistance to deformation.

2. 2 Response of Al honeycomb

A hydrodynamic response of the Al honeycomb was accounted for using the Mie-Grüneisen equation of state, while its deviatoric response was modelled using the linear elastic and Johnson-Cook plasticity models available in the ABAQUS/Explicit software package. An identical element-deletion strategy was used to remove excessively deformed elements from the simulation as discussed in Section 2.1.3.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Delamination patterns at the entry and exit sides of CFRP face sheets were studied using the developed FE model. The extent of delamination between adjacent plies after the projectile perforated the CFRP/Al-HC structure is shown in Figs. 3 A and B. It should be noted that though the FE model was quarter-symmetric, full delamination planes were obtained during the post-processing offering better observation of these results. The ply-level damage was also studied: here fibre damage/spallation was the dominant mode of damage. The fibre damage on the front and back faces of entry and exit side face sheets is shown in Figs. 4a and b. Shear-driven crushing of Al core directly below the point of impact was also evident from simulations. This was compared with the experimental results of [7] shown in Fig. 5A (The X-Z plane of simulation corresponds to the 2-3 plane of the experimental results). The cut-view showing the final configuration of the CFRP/Al-HC composite structure is presented in Fig. 5B.

Figure 3: Delamination of CFRP face sheet for entry (A) and exit (B) sides between adjacent plies: (a) 0° and 45°; (b) -45° and 45°; (c) 45° and 0°; (d) 45° and -45°.

$V_i = 1$ km/s. Projectile radius 3 mm

Figure 4: Fibre damage on surface of CFRP sheets at entry (a) and exit (b) sides. $V_i = 1$ km/s.
Projectile radius 3 mm

Figure 5: (A) Damage of Al-HC core: comparison of experiments (left) and FE model (right);
(B) cross-sectional view of final state of studied composite laminate showing surface peel up of CFRP
face sheets ($V_i = 1$ km/s)

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the response of the CFRP/Al-HC composite structure to hypervelocity impact with $V_i = 1$ km/s, projectile radius 3 mm was studied using a developed 3D finite element model. Damage to the CFRP face sheets was observed in terms of dynamic spall and surface peeling, while the Al-HC core failed due to core cracking driven by shear. The simulation results offer a reasonable agreement with experimental observations.

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